

PERSPECTIVE OPEN ACCESS

Light-Coupled Nanocrystal Solids

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ABSTRACT

Ordered assemblies of colloidal semiconductor nanocrystals have traditionally been studied for energy transfer and electronic transport arising from wavefunction overlap between neighboring nanocrystals. In this perspective, we instead focus on light-coupled nanocrystal solids engineered primarily for light emission. These materials include ordered superlattices and compositionally doped assemblies, spanning a continuum from optically dense solids in which all nanocrystals are emissive to optically diluted solids where emitters are spatially separated by transparent filler nanocrystals. By tuning emitter density and interparticle spacing relative to the emission wavelength, light-coupled nanocrystal solids enable access to optical regimes ranging from collective phenomena such as superfluorescence and superradiance to single-nanocrystal and single-photon emission. Rooted in lead halide perovskite and cadmium chalcogenide nanocrystal superlattices, this concept can be extended to heavy-metal-free nanocrystals and provides a materials platform for optical information processing and quantum technologies.

1 | Introduction

Wouldn't it be nice if a nanomaterial could be arranged into a lasing medium or a single-photon emitter, depending on the application? In Greek mythology, Amphion built a wall for the citadel of Thebes by moving stones by music following his playing of the lyre [1]. Colloidal nanocrystals bring us close to this idea of a universal light emitter, and self-assembly could be that magical music. Of course, this vision borders on wishful thinking. Achieving such modularity requires hard work and optimization, aptly expressed in one of the works behind the 2023 Nobel Prize in Chemistry for the discovery and synthesis of quantum dots: “*We do not believe the difference in quality of the optical spectra reflects any fundamental material limitations but rather the amount of effort spent in optimizing the growth conditions for each material.*” [2] The tension between the creative aspiration and practical effort shapes how chemists think about assembling materials from nanocrystals. Nanocrystal assemblies, or nanocrystal solids, are aesthetically striking, often serendipitous, and carry expectations of utility [3].

2 | Electronically Coupled Vs Light-Coupled Nanocrystal Solids

It is customary to fabricate nanocrystal solids – ordered arrays or superlattices and thin films – that have semiconductor nanocrystals close-packed to each other for an enhanced electronic coupling, energy transfer, and conductivity [4–9]. The existing approach to arrays of semiconductor nanocrystals (e.g., CdSe, PbSe) is rooted in optimizing electron transport [5, 6] rather than light emission. In contrast, the light-coupled nanocrystal solids are nanocrystal assemblies built to optimize light emission. Light-coupled nanocrystal solids are self-assembled nanocrystal materials in which the dominant interaction between individual nanocrystals is mediated by the electromagnetic field, rather than by electronic wavefunction overlap or charge transport. They are engineered so that optical coupling via emission, reabsorption, and collective radiative modes governs their functionality, enabling regimes ranging from cooperative emission to isolated single-emitter behavior. The ratio of inter-nanocrystal spacing to emission wavelength (s/λ_{em}) illustrates the crossover from collective radiative modes to single-emitter behavior, as well as the intermediate regime for nanomaterial engineering (Figure 1).

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FIGURE 1 | Light-coupled nanocrystal solids. Fraction of emitters for a simple cubic assembly of nanocrystals as a function of the ratio between inter-nanocrystal distance (s) and emission wavelength (λ_{em}) of the nanocrystal. By traversing the ratio s/λ_{em} from ca. 0.02 ($s=10$ nm, $\lambda_{em}=500$ nm) to 2 ($s=1000$ nm) by engineering the fraction of emitters, one spans functional regimes from collective photoluminescence to single-particle phenomena. ASE – amplified spontaneous emission, NC – nanocrystal.

Recent reviews have highlighted the emerging role of radiative coupling in nanocrystal assemblies and the self-assembly principles governing their formation [10, 11].

The concept of light-coupled nanocrystal solids became feasible thanks to the continuous development of luminescent colloidal nanocrystals, most recently spearheaded by lead halide perovskites. In less than 10 years since the synthesis of monodisperse colloidal CsPbX_3 ($X=\text{Cl, Br, I}$) nanocrystals by hot-injection [12], high-quality single-photon emission [13], multi-excitation superfluorescence [14], single-excitation superradiance [15], and photon indistinguishability [16] have been reported. These properties have been studied in nanocrystal superlattices ($s/\lambda_{em} < 0.1$) or isolated nanocrystals, free-standing or dispersed in a polymer matrix ($s/\lambda_{em} > 2$). Importantly for applications, these advancements motivate a shift in how colloidal nanocrystals are viewed: from inorganic luminophores tunable by quantum confinement and used in, e.g., consumer display technologies to building blocks of quantum materials relevant for optical information processing and quantum computing [17–19].

While single light-emitting nanocrystals are a familiar concept analogous to single fluorescent molecules, perovskite nanocrystal superlattices are entering an uncharted territory by combining an exceptional structural order for a colloidal solid [20–23] with nanocrystals that are intrinsically efficient light emitters. The CsPbBr_3 nanocrystal superlattices are microscopic solids made of close-packed and very well-ordered CsPbBr_3 nanocrystals (e.g., there is only 1.4 \AA of average displacement for 107 \AA center-to-center distance between nanocrystals [21]). It is tempting to draw an analogy between nanocrystal superlattices and crystals or aggregates of molecular fluorophores (e.g., J- and H-aggregates) [24, 25], particularly with respect to crystallinity and structural disorder [26], yet such a comparison becomes problematic when

extended to collective electronic properties. In molecular aggregates, point-dipole approximations are often adequate because of defined transition dipole moments and sub-nanometer intermolecular separations [27]. In contrast, nanocrystal solids involve multiple length scales, such as nanocrystal surface-to-surface and center-to-center separations, and less-defined transition dipole moments. Thus, rather than mapping nanocrystal superlattices, such as perovskite ones, directly onto molecular solids, we argue that it is useful to place them within a broader continuum of light-coupled nanocrystal solids. Along this continuum, an optically dense superlattice composed entirely of emitting nanocrystals represents one extreme, while an ordered, largely transparent solid doped with emissive nanocrystals represents the other. This progression is illustrated in Figure 2.

3 | From Dense to Dilute: Cooperative Emission in Light-Coupled Solids

There is a good reason to try to make materials along that continuum, that is to reduce the optical density of emitters. From a spectroscopic and optical standpoint, nanocrystal solids like CsPbBr_3 superlattices are optically thick and experience strong excitation attenuation, photoluminescence self-filtering (inner filter effect) due to the small Stokes shift, and inter-nanocrystal energy transfer (concentration quenching) that might interfere with cooperative emission. The large absorption cross-section of CsPbBr_3 nanocrystals and high volume density of nanocrystals ($\sim 1 \cdot 10^{18}$ nanocrystals/ cm^3) result in a quick attenuation of the excitation beam within the first 100 nm^{-1} micron of the superlattice, depending on the excitation wavelength [28, 29]. As a consequence, the topmost nanocrystals in an optically dense nanocrystal solid are highly excited with multiple electron-hole pairs, while the innermost nanocrystals are weakly or not excited at all. Overall, this results in a spatially heterogeneous distribution of excited nanocrystals, in contrast to the uniformly excited ensemble as in superfluorescent samples of molecular or atomic gases [30, 31].

FIGURE 2 | Illustration of the transition from an optically dense single-component colloidal nanocrystal superlattice to a binary superlattice by introducing second, wide-gap (“transparent”) nanocrystals and further towards an optically dilute nanocrystal solid. Perfect green cubes are used as an artistic representation of CsPbBr_3 colloidal nanocrystals.

Fortunately, cooperative emission might not require very close proximity between nanocrystals. One relevant length scale for cooperative emission like Dicke superradiance [32] is the optical confinement volume, $V \sim \lambda_{\text{em}}^3$, where λ_{em} is the emission wavelength. Within this volume, a collective state can emerge through the synchronous alignment of excited dipoles, as if they were coupled by a shared oscillating electromagnetic field extending over a length scale set by λ_{em} . For example, Dicke superradiance (close to what has been called superfluorescence in nanocrystals) has been reported in a dilute hydrogen fluoride (HF) gas, 1.3 mTorr at room temperature, or a number density of 10^{13} molecules/cm³ for $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 84 \mu\text{m}$ [30] or a vapor of Na atoms (10^9 – 10^{10} atoms/cm³ for $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 2.21 \mu\text{m}$ and $3.41 \mu\text{m}$) [33], where the nearest emitter-emitter distance is much larger than the emitter's size and several orders of magnitude less emitter density than in optically dense nanocrystal superlattices. Extending this analogy to nanocrystals is not straightforward. Unlike small molecules or atoms, nanocrystals are in the regime where the ratio between λ_{em} and the emitter size is orders of magnitude smaller. For example, it is approximately 50–60 for typical CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals ($\lambda_{\text{em}} = 500 \text{ nm}$ and ~ 8 – 10 nm nanocrystal size) compared to 10^5 – 10^3 for HF molecules and Na atoms. Nevertheless, starting from optically dense nanocrystal solids and progressively increasing the separation between emissive nanocrystals could enable access to tunable collective emission. Practically, such light-coupled nanocrystal solids are realized by a co-assembly of emissive and transparent nanocrystals.

Considering lead-based metal halides, there is a variety of nanocrystal compositions to design light-coupled nanocrystal solids with photoluminescence across the visible spectrum and beyond (Figure 3). Cube-shaped CsPbX₃ nanocrystals (Figure 3A) are likely to remain the emitter of choice, thanks to the combination of photophysical properties and emission tunability by confinement and composition extending to near infrared (Figure 3B,C). Several metal halide nanocrystal compositions are available for use as transparent fillers (Figure 3D). In choosing a matching component, one should consider chemical compatibility so that, unless intentionally designed, a cation, anion, or substantial ligand exchange does not occur and alter the properties of emitter nanocrystals. For the emissive CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals, wide-gap CsBr

[34], LaF₃ [35], NaGdF₄ [36, 37], or compositionally congruent Cs₄PbBr₆ nanocrystals [38] could serve as matching components. The tuning of the nanocrystal solid composition from optically dense ($s \approx 2 \text{ nm}$, separation between the emissive nanocrystals) to intermediate ($s \approx 10 \text{ nm}$ or larger) and dilute ($s \sim \lambda_{\text{em}}$) spans five orders of magnitude of the emitter number density, from $[N] \sim 1 \cdot 10^{18}$ to $6 \cdot 10^{16}$ and $\leq 8 \cdot 10^{13}$ nanocrystals/cm³, respectively (estimated for 8 nm edge length nanocubes with a 2 nm-thick ligand shell and $\lambda_{\text{em}} \approx 500$). The excitation attenuation drops by a factor of ~ 100 when moving to the intermediate composition, enabling uniform excitation penetration throughout the entire solid of nanocrystals.

4 | Heavy-Metal-Free Nanocrystals: Motivation and Opportunity

Beyond perovskites and compared to the ubiquitous nanocrystal assemblies made from cadmium and lead-containing nanocrystals, there are few reports of nanocrystal superlattices made from other nanocrystal emitters. The assemblies are often limited to indium pnictides (InP, InAs-based nanocrystals) and are documented through electron microscopy images as evidence of high nanocrystal synthesis uniformity [39] but are rare subjects of study [40]. A similar situation exists with CuInS₂ nanocrystals, in which assemblies are studied for structural characterization and transformation [41–43]. The situation is worse for ZnSe and Ag₂S nanocrystals. The lack of studies on superlattices of these nanocrystals is likely due to the unclear purpose of the resulting materials. This is understandable, given that early reports characterized nanocrystals by broad size distributions and low photoluminescence quantum yields. Thanks to the perseverance of numerous groups worldwide, the quality of nanocrystals, in terms of both uniformity and emission efficiency, is improving. The conditions under which high-quality, heavy-metal-free nanocrystals can self-assemble have now been established, creating the possibility of engineering light-coupled nanomaterials from them.

Regulations push toward heavy-metal-free nanocrystal compositions. For example, in Europe, the long-standing exemption allowing Cd-based quantum dots in displays has recently been

FIGURE 3 | Lead halide-based nanocrystal building blocks for light-coupled nanocrystal solids. (A) Lead halide perovskite nanocrystal emitters and their photophysical properties make them attractive for light-coupled nanocrystal solids. (B) Mini-library of light-coupled nanocrystal solids building blocks. Excitonic emitters with small Stokes shift illustrate compositional tunability of λ_{em} in the lead halide perovskite nanocrystals by anion and cation exchange. (C) Dopant emitters with a large Stokes shift could be metal halides doped with transition-metal or rare-earth-metal ions. (D) Wide-gap “transparent” nanocrystals are binary, ternary, or quaternary metal halides encompassing simple ionic salts, 0D metal halides, double perovskites, or Ruddlesden-Popper mixed compositions.

phased out [44]. This motivates the studies of heavy-metal-free nanocrystal emitter chemistries that can deliver advanced optical functions while remaining compatible with sustainability goals. It might also be overly simplistic to anticipate that heavy-metal-free materials replicate the performance of Pb-/Cd-based ones [45]. Some optical technologies remain enabled by specific elements, for example, Ti^{3+} ions in Ti:sapphire lasers [46]. Thus, the pursuit of heavy-metal-free light-coupled nanocrystal solids should be viewed as an expansion of the design space to find out which collective properties are universal, and which are specific to electronic structures of, e.g., lead halide perovskites.

The indium phosphide (InP-based) nanocrystals, metal chalcogenides (specifically ternary CuInS_2 , binary ZnSe, Ag_2S), and Pb-free metal halides (Mn- and Cu-based compositions) are the highly emissive colloidal nanocrystals with greener compositions. Each class has its benefits and shortcomings. For example, InP-based nanocrystals feature an isotropic bright exciton [47] compatible with superradiance and are the most studied materials in terms of electronic structure, single-photon emission [48, 49], and large-scale production (Figure 4A). CuInS_2 -based nanocrystals are synthetically optimized for high quantum yield and manufactured on an industrial scale (Figure 4B). The shortcomings of CuInS_2 nanocrystals are defects, spectral diffusion, and slow radiative lifetimes (10s–100s ns

at room temperature and μs at cryogenic conditions) [52, 57, 58]. ZnSe-based and Ag_2S nanocrystals are synthetically optimized with achievable high photoluminescence quantum yields (PLQYs) [54, 59] yet modestly studied photonic chalcogenides (Figure 4C). Mn/Cu-based metal halides exhibit bright emission (Figure 4D) from delocalized and self-trapped excitons, making them attractive superradiant platforms. The Mn/Cu-based halide nanocrystals lag behind their Pb-based counterparts in size and shape control and in the discovery of photonic properties, but these materials are catching up [60]. Although many of the abovementioned nanocrystals have, at first glance, sub-optimal optical properties, for example, slow radiative emission, it is worth investigating the optical properties of their close-packed assemblies and checking for light amplification. Cryo-optical setups, which were once exclusive to physics labs, are now commercially available and can be integrated into chemistry groups and laboratories [61].

5 | Transparent Nanocrystals as Optical Spacers

At least two classes of materials yield nanocrystals that are transparent in the visible and near-infrared regions, suitable for use as diluents in light-coupled nanocrystal solids. These classes are

FIGURE 4 | Classes of heavy-metal-free (e.g., Pb/Cd-free) nanocrystals for self-assembly into light-coupled nanocrystal solids: (A) InP@ZnSe nanocrystals with $\text{PLQY} > 50\%$ feature broad ensemble spectra with pure single-photon emission at the level of individual nanocrystals, fast radiative recombination, and stability under high excitation intensity [50]; (B) size-tunable and uniform CuInS_2 [51] nanocrystals are suitable building blocks for assembly, despite slow emission [52] their high PLQY relatives – $\text{CuIn}(\text{Se};\text{S})_2/\text{ZnS}$ — are produced on a 55-gallon drum scale [53]; (C) emissive ZnSe@ZnS with reduced blinking (multicomponent photoluminescence lifetimes 1–30 ns, tunable by the growth conditions) [54] and uniform Ag_2S [55] nanocrystals are binary sulfides for nanocrystal solids; (D) an example of bright ($\text{PLQY} \sim 54\%$) and fast Mn-based halide nanocrystal emitters [56] that still require synthetic optimization. Some of the images are adapted with permission from refs [50, 52, 55], respectively. Copyright 2021, 2017, 2007, American Chemical Society. Photos of the 55-gallon drum full of nanocrystals are adapted with permission from ref [53]. Copyright 2021, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co.

FIGURE 5 | Wide-gap (transparent) filler nanocrystals. (A) Uniform polygonal tin-doped indium oxide single-crystalline nanocrystals self-assemble into close-packed multilayers and have a broad optical transparency window [62]; (B) binary alkali halide nanocrystals feature a variety of shapes from polygonal to cubic and have a wide optical transparency window extending to UV below 250 nm (for chlorides and bromides) [34, 63]. Figures are adapted with permission from refs [62, 36], respectively. Copyright 2012, 2018, American Chemical Society.

metal oxides (e.g., indium tin oxide ($\text{Sn:In}_2\text{O}_3$), MgO, Figure 5A) and wide-gap metal halides (e.g., KI, CsBr, RbBr, Figure 5B). These nanocrystals often have surface chemistry (fatty acids and amines) similar to that of the emissive nanocrystals. Moreover, the composition of these nanocrystals makes them chemically inert toward cation exchange reactions that could alter the composition of emissive chalcogenides. For emissive metal halides, the anion exchange reaction is facile. In that case, simply matching the halide between an emissive nanocrystal and a transparent one (e.g., CsMnBr_3 and CsBr) would prevent undesirable chemical reactions. The filler nanocrystals of both classes appear as either off-white/grey (oxides) or colorless (halides) and transparent dispersions in common organic solvents; their optical spectra do not contain electronic transitions that overlap with absorption spectra of emissive nanocrystals. The synthetic control over filler nanocrystals reached the level where they spontaneously assemble into monocomponent superlattices with colloidal crystal symmetry dependent on the shape of individual nanocrystals.

6 | From Beauty to Function

Since the early reports of nanocrystal superlattices three decades ago [64], colloidal superlattices have been supplying researchers with nature-like power to create artificial crystals. At the same time, it is not uncommon to hear criticism of these beautiful materials due to their lack of use. The lack of practical application or strong commercial demand for one is strikingly contrasted with the commercialization of colloidal quantum dots and the products containing them; most notably, QLED TVs are now available in electronics stores worldwide. Despite the high profile of nanocrystal self-assembly, colloidal superlattices are still finding their way into the manufacturing chain and a commercial device. This gap is characteristic of the ‘valley of death’ separating low

technology readiness levels (TRLs 1-4) focused on discovery from technologies mature enough for societal deployment (TRLs 7-9).

Colloidal superlattices provide a platform for rich and challenging collective physics, yet their broader use in applications remains limited relative to simpler materials, although application-relevant properties are emerging across catalysis and photonics [65–68]. One reason for optimism is a historic analogy: epitaxial semiconductor superlattices – the ancestors and namesakes of colloidal ones – also originated as platforms for fundamental studies before becoming foundational in devices like a quantum cascade laser [69]. Continuing experimental and theoretical investigations of light-coupled nanocrystal solids could be a pathway to address their utility and to put them on the map (and, in the future, on the chip) of emerging photonics circuits that are becoming the basis of optical quantum technology [70, 71]. To achieve that, one illustrative demonstration could be the incorporation of a nanocrystal solid into a device like a random number generator. A random quantum number generator is one of the components used in quantum information technology [72], with recent implementations including a perovskite light-emitting diode [73].

Figure 6 outlines the schematic of the proposed device. In the ideal case, the fluctuations of the phase or photon number (amplitude) of the collective emission from a nanocrystal solid would serve as a digitizable source of randomness upon their detection with an appropriate setup. Figure 6 shows a Mach-Zehnder interferometer setup for the detection of phase fluctuations by monitoring the differential signal from the bright and dark outputs of the interferometer. The large number of nanocrystals coupled together in a superfluorescent mode would accelerate the emission rate as $\tau_{\text{SR}} \sim 1/N$, where N is the number of emitters. For nanocrystals with λ_{em} in the 400–1500 nm range, this translates to tens of thousands of coupled emitters, resulting in a GHz-THz bitrate of

FIGURE 6 | Quantum random number generator based on collective photoluminescence from light-coupled nanocrystal solids.

random number generation. Random number generators based on colloidal nanocrystals will present a low-cost alternative to single-photon sources. The intrinsic heterogeneity of nanocrystals is anticipated to combine with the inherent randomness of cooperative emission to yield a high-performance microscopic source of light and information, while solution processability could facilitate on-chip manufacturing.

7 | Outlook

As light is complementary to electricity, light-coupled nanocrystal solids are complementary to electronically coupled nanocrystal assemblies and provide a versatile experimental platform for investigating and designing cooperative emission. To advance the research and development of light-coupled nanocrystal solids, numerous challenges remain. Some of them are practical, such as the unambiguous characterization of collective emission, the repeatable and scalable manufacturing, and the deterministic manipulation. Beyond crystal growth and patterning, scalability will also depend on developing light-coupled nanocrystal solids in practical materials formats, such as powders or composites embedded in polymeric or inorganic matrices, while retaining their optical coupling and structural integrity. Some challenges are more fundamental, such as formally defining the coupling between nanocrystals, going beyond the point-dipole approximation in describing inter-nanocrystal interactions, and determining whether structural order is a necessary precondition for collective phenomena or a by-product of self-assembly. There is continuous progress, such as scalable manufacturing by microfluidic techniques [74–76], protective shelling by metal oxide ALD [77], micromechanical manipulation by grippers [78], directed growth by printing or in patterned substrates [67, 79, 80], expanding range of structures and compositions [37], and theoretical comprehension of superlattice dimensionality and disorder in superradiance [81–84]. This non-exhaustive list of advances suggests that the future of light-coupled nanocrystal solids will be shaped by a combination of creative self-assembly and functional utility, much like Amphion's music once guided stones into functional structure.

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Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

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